

A Data-driven, AI –Enabled Approach to Predict Crystal Morphology Evolution in Semi-crystalline Thermoplastic Composites

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“to build an AI-enabled inverse design approach for fundamental understanding and integrated material-manufacturing design of advanced polymer composites.”

<https://www.energyfrontier.us/node/6537>

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Introduction – Thermoplastic Composites

- › Thermoplastics have been extensively used for non-structural and semi-structural purposes in electronics, automotive^{[1], [2], [3]} and marine^[4] applications.
- › Additionally, there is noticeable interest in adopting continuous fiber reinforcements in thermoplastic composites in:
 - structural applications^[4]
 - hydrogen storage (Type IV and Type V pressure vessels)^[5],
 - medical prosthetics^[6]
 - conformal electronics^{[7], [8]}
 - sports equipment
- › Globally, 7 to 9 million tons of thermoplastics were used as part of FRP composite systems^[4].

Figure 1: Growth in use of plastics and composites in passenger vehicles^[1]

[1] S. A. Pradeep, S. Shukla, N. Brown, and S. Pilla, "Thermoplastics Foams: An Automotive Perspective," in *Lightweight and Sustainable Materials for Automotive Applications*, CRC Press, 2017, pp. 369–400. doi: 10.1201/9781315152967-11.
 [2] S. A. Pradeep et al., "A Perspective on the Evolution of Plastics and Composites in the Automotive Industry," *Applied Plastics Engineering Handbook*, pp. 705–748, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-323-88667-3.00016-3.
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 [4] J. Zhang, G. Lin, U. Vaidya, and H. Wang, "Past, present and future prospective of global carbon fibre composite developments and applications," *Compos B Eng*, vol. 250, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2022.110463.
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 [8] K. Wu, Q. Zhou, H. Zou, K. Leng, Y. Zeng, and Z. Wu, "High Precision Thermoforming 3D-Conformable Electronics with a Phase-Changing Adhesion Interlayer," *Micromachines* 2019, Vol. 10, Page 160, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 160, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.3390/M10030160.

Introduction – Manufacturing with Thermoplastic Composites

- › Filler and fibers introduced in various forms to enhance mechanical properties.
- › Trade-off in terms of added manufacturing complexity, and limitations in manufacturable geometries.
- › General physics of manufacturing remains consistent across various thermoplastic composite manufacturing processes.
 - Heating:
 - pellets/filament/sheet heating above melt temperature (T_m)
 - Material Flow:
 - Suspension flow
 - Extrusion of melt
 - Draping of sheet
 - Cooling to near room temperature (T_{RT})

Figure 2: A Qualitative comparison of thermoplastic composite manufacturing processes

Figure 3: Discretization of process steps in thermoplastic composites manufacturing

Introduction – Semi-crystalline Thermoplastics and Crystallization

- › Thermoplastics are divided into two broad categories:
 - semi-crystalline thermoplastics
 - amorphous thermoplastics
- › Semi-crystalline thermoplastics form ordered structures or crystals in certain locations as polymer chains align as the thermoplastic cools.

- › The cooling step, that crosses the recrystallization temperature (T_{RC}) influences the microstructure of the manufactured thermoplastic composite part.
- › Microstructure influences mechanical properties.

Figure 5: Thermoplastic Materials Pyramid

Figure 6: Behavior of Semi-crystalline and Amorphous Thermoplastics [9]

Figure 7: Cooling dynamics for a forming process for semi-crystalline thermoplastics composites

[9] <https://madisongroup.com/the-importance-of-crystallinity-in-plastics-performance/>

Motivation

› Why is crystal morphology and its evolution important?

- Different crystalline phase distributions within homogeneous polymer results in different mechanical properties.

Table 1: Effect of different crystalline phases of i-PP on mechanical behavior

Monoclinic α -PP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher strength • Higher stiffness 	Typical cooling
Trigonal β -PP ^[10]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher toughness • lower stiffness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supercooling • Varying temperature gradients • Shear • <u>Nucleating agents</u>

- Smaller spherulites result in improved impact strength, tensile strength and lower water absorption rate. ^[11]
- Addition of fillers change the oriented crystalline phase distributions. ^[12]

Table 2: Effect of different processes and presence of filler on crystalline phase distributions for PA6

Compression Molding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pure PA6: α-PA6 + γ - PA6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PA6 + clay: γ - PA6
Cast Extrusion Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pure PA6: γ - PA6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PA6 + clay: higher γ - PA6

- **How do we identify the right processing parameters, polymer attributes and fiber/filler to achieve desired mechanical or chemical properties?**

➡ **THROUGH EXPERIENCE ... OR WE UTILIZE PREDICTIVE MODELS**

[10] Varga, J. (2002). β -MODIFICATION OF ISOTACTIC POLYPROPYLENE: PREPARATION, STRUCTURE, PROCESSING, PROPERTIES, AND APPLICATION. Journal of Macromolecular Science, Part B, 41(4-6), 1121-1171. <https://doi.org/10.1081/MB-120013089>
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 [12] <https://doi.org/10.1002/pen.23813>

Motivation – Need for Data-driven, AI-enabled models

- Most existing models are semi-analytical i.e. they depend on:
 - Experimental data to calibrate model constants
 - Empirically derived relationships

Hoffman-Lauritzen Growth Model [13]
$$G = G_0 \exp\left(-\frac{U^*}{R(T-T_\infty)}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{K_g}{fT\Delta T}\right)$$

G = Growth speed
 G₀ = pre-exponential factor determined experimentally
 U* = Activation Energy
 K_g = kinetic parameter for nucleation
 F = correction factor
 T_∞ = T_g – 30 K

Table 3: Nucleation and Growth Models

	Nucleation Models [14]	Intrinsic Material Parameters		Process Parameters				
		Molecular weight	Presence of fiber	Thermal History	Isothermal	Non-isothermal (Cooling Rate)	Pressure	Shear Rate
Extended Volume Approach	Avrami (1939)	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No
	Nakamura (1972)	No	No	No	Yes	Yes (considering successive isothermal stages)	No	No
Probabilistic Approach	Kolmogoroff (1937)	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No
	Evans (1945)	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No
	Ozawa (1971)	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
ODE	Haudin and Chenote	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Geometrical	Schneider's Formalism (1988)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Possible	Possible

[13] Lauritzen JI, Hoffman JD. Theory of formation of polymer crystals with folded chains in dilute solution. J Res Natl Bureau Standards Sect A Phys Chem. 1960;64A(1):73. doi:10.6028/jres.064A.007

[14] <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/pat.5918>

Figure 8: Approach for experimental data generation, post-processing and representative model development

Materials Selected for the Study

Fiber 1 : PAN-based Carbon Fiber [15]
 T300, 12K Tow, Toray
 Sizing burnt off at 600 °C

Fiber 2 : Glass Fiber [16]

A) S-Glass (from literature)
 SiO₂ (65%), Al₂O₃ (25%) and MgO (10%)
 B) E-Glass (Hexcel Hexforce 7781)
 Spec'd out for additional trials.

Fiber 3: Flax Fiber [17][18]

Fiber name	Mass content in %				
	Cellulose	Hemicelluloses	Lignin	Pectin	Waxes
Abaca	62.5	21	12	0.8	3
Alfa	45.4	38.5	14.9	-	2
Bamboo	34.5	20.5	26	-	-
Cotton	89	4	0.75	6	0.6
Flax	70.5	16.5	2.5	0.9	-
Hemp	81	20	4	0.9	0.8
Jute	67	16	9	0.2	0.5
Kenaf	53.5	21	17	2	-
Sisal	60	11.5	8	1.2	-

- High purity and controlled MW distribution polymer samples procured from Scientific Polymer Products, USA.

Approx Mn	10,000
Density	1.36 g/cc
Tg	150 C
Tm	285 C

Approx Mw	25,000
Density	1.14 g/cc (@23 C)
Tg	62.5 C
Tm	220 C

Approx Mw	25,000
Density	0.9 g/cc (@23 C)
Tg	-26 C
Tm	160 C

[15] <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.08.023>
 [16] <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-019-40524-7>
 [17] <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ma9020093>
 [18] Thesis. (2021). Quan Nguyen CHEMICAL MODIFICATION OF NATURAL FIBERS AND OPTIMIZING THE PROCESSING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BY COMPRESSING MOLDING METHOD.

Experimental Methodology

› Parallel Plate Rheometer (TA Instruments RH2) used.

› 0.5N axial force, $T_{max} = T_{melt} + 20C$

Figure 9: Sample preparation method for transmission-Polarized Light Microscopy (t-PLM)

› Nikon Eclipse LV100N with a 20x objective, 5 MP camera and a Linkam Hotstage for varying cooling rates was utilized.

Figure 10: transmission-Polarized Light Microscopy (t-PLM) Setup

Table 4: Experimental Matrix for Cooling rate effects investigation

Matrix	CF	GF	Flax	Neat
i-PP	1C/min	1C/min	1C/min	1C/min
	5C/min	5C/min	5C/min	5C/min
	10C/min	10C/min	10C/min	10C/min
	20C/min	20C/min	20C/min	20C/min
PA6	1C/min	1C/min	Fiber Degrades for Processing Temperature of Thermoplastic Matrix	1C/min
	5C/min	5C/min		5C/min
	10C/min	10C/min		10C/min
	20C/min	20C/min		20C/min
PPS	1C/min	1C/min	Fiber Degrades for Processing Temperature of Thermoplastic Matrix	1C/min
	5C/min	5C/min		5C/min
	10C/min	10C/min		10C/min
	20C/min	20C/min		20C/min

Neat iso-PP crystallization

Flax-PP crystallization

Time Temperature Curves

AI Model Development Approach

- G = Crystal growth rate (m/s)
- G_0 = Pre-exponential factor
- U^* = Activation energy for chain motion
- R = Gas constant
- K_g = Kinetic growth parameter
- $\Delta T = T_0 - T$ = Supercooling
- $f = 2T/\Delta T$ = Correction factor
- \dot{N} is the nucleation rate
- ϕ_0 = Extended crystalline volume fraction
- R_i = Radius of individual crystalline structures

Feature Extraction

- Convolution layer
- Batch normalization
- Max-pooling
- Flatten

Features along with temperature and time were fed into the network

$$\phi_{tr}^0(t) = \frac{X_f}{1 - X_f} \cdot \frac{1}{R_f^2} [(R_f + e(t))^2 - R_f^2]$$

X_f : fiber volume fraction

R_f : fiber radius

$e(t)$: transcrySTALLINE layer thickness

Next Steps

- › Experimentation
 - Incorporation of additional physical conditions such as :
 - Shear: For GF/iPP composites, transcrystalline zone appeared only when the fiber is pulled out from the melt or when shear stress is applied at given crystallization temperature [19], [20].
 - Investigation of polymer blends such as TPOs (PP + EPDM + carbon black)
 - Incorporation of XRD to provide associated crystal orientation distribution information.
- › Extraction of Nucleation rate, Radial growth rate, Crystalline volume fraction change through image segmentation
 - Dragonfly © software enables image segmentation for time successive images.
- › Validation of extracted feature information from CNN against data extracted through image segmentation.
- › Utilize trained Physics-informed CNN to predict microstructure morphology evolution.

[19] Varga, J., Karger-Kocsis, J. Direct evidence of row-nucleated cylindritic crystallization in glass fiber-reinforced polypropylene composites. Polymer Bulletin 30, 105–110 (1993). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00296241>

[20] Campbell, D. and Qayyum, M.M. (1980), Melt crystallization of polypropylene: Effect of contact with fiber substrates. J. Polym. Sci. Polym. Phys. Ed., 18: 83-93. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pol.1980.180180107>

Acknowledgements

- › This work was supported as part of the AIM for Composites, an Energy Frontier Research Center funded by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, Basic Energy Sciences at the University of Delaware under award #DE-SC0023389.
- › The authors would like to acknowledge Dr. Steve Sauerbrunn for sharing his insights that contributed towards experimental work.

BACK UP SLIDES

Extract images at specific sampling rate

```
from google.colab import drive
drive.mount('/content/drive')

!ls

import cv2
import os

# Function to extract and save frames from a video
def extract_frames(video_path, output_dir, sample_rate=10):
    # Ensure the output directory exists
    if not os.path.exists(output_dir):
        os.makedirs(output_dir)

    # Open the video file
    video = cv2.VideoCapture(video_path)

    # Get total number of frames in the video
    total_frames = int(video.get(cv2.CAP_PROP_FRAME_COUNT))
    fps = int(video.get(cv2.CAP_PROP_FPS))

    # Define sample rate (e.g., 1 image every 'sample_rate' frames)
    count = 0
    saved_frame_count = 0

    while True:
        success, frame = video.read()

        if not success:
            break

        # Save every 'sample_rate' frames
        if count % sample_rate == 0:
            frame_filename = os.path.join(output_dir, f'frame_{saved_frame_count}.jpg')
            cv2.imwrite(frame_filename, frame)
            saved_frame_count += 1

        count += 1

    video.release()
    print(f'Extraction complete. {saved_frame_count} frames saved.')

extract_frames('/content/drive/MyDrive/Colab_Notebooks/PLM_Videos/PLM_Videos/PLM_Deepin_11
```


Normalized Intensity Histogram based Segmentation

Extracting Nucleation rate, radial Growth rate from segmented Images (In-Progress)